

University Education and Internal Labour Migration Outcomes of Recent Graduates

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Abstract

The paper examines post-educational interregional migration of recent Russian university graduates as one of the key factors in the redistribution of human capital between regions. Based on individual data on more than 250.000 graduates of 2021, the paper analyses the characteristics that influence migration decisions and assesses the wage premium/penalty received after relocation. The results presented in this paper show that educational characteristics (source of educational funding, presence of a diploma with honours, continuation of education, average admission exam score) have the most significant impact on migration decisions. The assessment of the modified Mincer equation also made it possible to determine the return on migration. Thus, moving to a more economically developed region provides an average wage increase of 10–17%. The greatest benefits from migration are enjoyed by graduates in medicine and agriculture, as well as STEM graduates, while representatives of the social sciences and education face a comparatively low return on relocation. The results confirm the hypothesis of high regional and sectoral differentiation in the Russian labour market. The study highlights the need for closer integration between the education system and regional labour markets in order to mitigate territorial imbalances in the distribution of human capital.

Keywords

graduate labour market, post-educational migration, regional heterogeneity, returns from migration, administrative data, Mincer equation

JEL codes: J24, J31, J61

Introduction

Internal migration serves as one of the main channels for the redistribution of labour resources, especially in the context of substantial institutional differentiation among Russian regions (Denisenko and Chernina 2017; Mkrtchyan and Florinskaya 2018b). Over the past decade, both the structure of migration and the motives driving individuals to relocate have changed. For instance, quality-of-life factors, such as the ecological environment and health system indicators, are increasingly considered alongside labour market characteristics, significantly influencing migration decisions (Vakulenko 2019).

Russian researchers also view population relocation as a key indicator of a country's economic development. In particular, the internal migration of university graduates is of special interest because graduates accumulate highly demanded skills and knowledge in the labour market. Notably, alumni migrate more intensively than older population groups, both within educational and post-educational migration streams (Mkrtchyan 2017; Mkrtchyan and Florinskaya 2018a). Educational migration typically refers to relocation for the purpose of obtaining initial higher education, whereas post-educational migration focuses on career opportunities after graduation (*ibid.*).

Consequently, the massive outflow of young specialists contributes to greater economic heterogeneity between donor and recipient regions in terms of human capital endowment and cumulative economic growth (Antosik and Ivashina 2021; Borzykh 2022). Regional differences in socio-economic indicators are therefore amplified, since the continuous accumulation of human capital remains a key factor for sustainable economic growth (Schultz 1961; Becker 1962). Moreover, the high differentiation of regional labour markets complicates the problem above. Researchers continue to observe inter-regional differences in the unemployment rate, labour force structure and, most significantly, in wages (Oshchepkov and Kapelyushnikov 2015). Therefore, young people are moving to other regions in search of higher income. According to Ravenstein's migration theory, individuals always move from low-income regions to high-income ones looking for better life conditions, including labour market prospects (Ravenstein 1889). Current regional policy, on the contrary, is still trying to smooth regional differences and achieve steady economic development. Taking these peculiarities into account, we try to determine the main factors affecting the migration decisions and evaluate returns from migration in the Russian labour market at the individual-data level.

This paper examines the post-educational labour migration of graduates, using educational and job characteristics as the main determinants of internal migration. With a focus on the Russian context, we pay special attention to the estimation of wage premiums following inter-regional migration. The article is structured into four parts. The first section reviews the literature on internal migration in Russia and other countries, with particular emphasis on the incentives to migrate and the outcomes of migration, especially for recent graduates.

The second section, Data and Methodology, describes the dataset and the regression models employed. This study utilizes a unique nationwide dataset, the "Monitoring of Graduates' Employment", which provides individual-level observations on education, employment, and wages across all Russian regions. The methodological approach centers on a Mincer equation with Heckman correction to estimate the returns from migration among graduates, capturing wage differences between migrants and non-migrants. Additionally, a Heck-

man-corrected probit model is applied to identify the most significant drivers of graduates' internal migration.

The final two sections are devoted to the presentation of Results and the Discussion.

Literature review

Causes and Effects of Internal Labour Migration

Regional differentiation significantly influences individual decisions regarding labour market behaviour. Numerous studies worldwide emphasize the relevance of youth migration and identify recent graduates as key drivers of economic development (Busch and Weigert 2008; Di Cintio and Grassi 2011; Liu and Shen 2014; González-Leonardo et al. 2022). Research also shows that young people, who in some contexts constitute more than half of all migrants (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2010; Bernard et al. 2014), often migrate to obtain high-quality education or secure employment with higher wages (Knapp 2013).

Cross-regional labour migration after graduation has attracted particular scholarly attention because the motives for relocation and its outcomes are not directly related to educational or family considerations. In other words, researchers focus on the pure effects of migration (Di Cintio and Grassi 2011). Career advancement and wage increases are therefore among the primary outcomes of post-educational migration, and studies suggest that returns from post-educational relocation are realized more rapidly than those from educational migration (Nowok et al. 2013).

Nonetheless, migration may yield mixed results, as migrants often experience losses in social networks, educational opportunities, and job connections. Empirical evidence documents several successful cases with substantial returns from migration for graduates (Yankow 1999; Venhorst and Cörvers 2018; Ward 2022). At the same time, alumni frequently encounter challenges; for instance, they may struggle to adapt to new labour market conditions (Alexander 2021). Such difficulties can delay the accumulation of human capital and partially affect productivity and job satisfaction [ibid.].

This raises the question: what evidence exists regarding post-educational migration in Russia?

Russian Specifics of Labour Migration

The issue of substantial regional differentiation in Russia is linked to several unique characteristics, making it a significant and interesting area of research. First, many Russian regions differ simultaneously in terms of economic structure, gross regional product (GRP) levels, social and healthcare indicators, cultural factors, the quality of higher education institutions, and, of course, labour market conditions (Oshchepkov and Kapelyushnikov 2015). Consequently, uncertainty regarding the most favourable region for relocation influences individual migration decisions.

Second, internal migration patterns in Russia differ from those observed in other countries. Unlike in many developed nations, the peak of migration activity occurs among the youngest working-age population, reflecting the early start of education and careers (Gabbrakhmanov 2019; Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2021). Previous studies also indicate that Russia exhibits lower overall migration flows compared to some developed countries such as the USA, the United Kingdom, and Australia, while showing patterns similar to Germany

and exceeding those of the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Poland (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2021). Therefore, special attention should be given to migration occurring during the school-to-work transition.

Third, the effectiveness of regional labour markets is closely correlated with the overall economic development of a region (Oshchepkov and Kapelyushnikov 2015). A consistent pattern can be observed in Russia, with migrants moving from the East to the West and from the South to the North (Mkrtchyan and Florinskaya 2018b; Gabdrakhmanov 2019; Emelina et al. 2022). Researchers have identified leading regions that consistently attract migrants, as well as “outsider” regions from which outgoing flows originate.

The strongest leaders are Moscow and Saint Petersburg, which feature a concentration of high-quality universities, a wide range of employment opportunities across various sectors, and favourable living conditions. These agglomerations are characterized by both high standards of living and strong labour market indicators, particularly high wages (Mkrtchyan and Florinskaya 2018a, 2018b; Gabdrakhmanov 2019). Another group of leading regions includes areas primarily specializing in mining and manufacturing, such as the Ural, Siberian, and Far Eastern regions. These regions are associated with high wages but limited social infrastructure and underdeveloped healthcare systems. Employment in these regions also has specific requirements, often depending on specialized skills and constrained labour demand (usually this refers to oil-producing regions with rotational employment).

In contrast, the Southern and Caucasian regions typically experience high unemployment rates, low-quality jobs, and low wage levels, placing them in the second group [ibid.]. These territories are characterized by both weaker labour market conditions and lower living standards.

Factors Influencing Post-Educational Migration among Young People

Several key studies focus specifically on youth and graduate migration in Russia. The most significant factors influencing graduates’ migration decisions are wages, as well as regional levels of poverty and unemployment (Antosik and Ivashina 2021). The authors also note that young people are often attracted to dynamic labour markets, where job search times are minimized, a wide selection of vacancies is available, and wages are flexible.

However, not all graduates relocate to Moscow or Saint Petersburg. Many choose smaller economic centres near their home region or the region where they studied (Antosik and Ivashina 2021). Furthermore, the decision to relocate among young professionals is strongly influenced by the opportunity to find employment that matches their skill level. This tendency is particularly evident in migration toward regions engaged in innovation and research (Moskvina 2019). For example, some graduates move to the Far Eastern territories, which are rich in natural resources and provide opportunities for research activities [ibid.].

The quality of higher education institutions also plays a vital role in migration decisions, both for educational and post-educational migration (Kashnitsky et al. 2016; Moskvina 2019; Borzykh 2022). For recent graduates, regions with high-quality educational institutions can serve as a positive signal of a more developed socio-economic environment, thereby increasing the attractiveness of migration to those areas (Bernard et al. 2014).

In summary, post-educational migration in Russia is shaped by specific characteristics of both regional educational systems and labour markets. These, in turn, influence individual migration decisions and migration outcomes. At the same time, university graduates

retain valuable human capital that lagging regions need to bridge existing gaps (Antosik and Ivashina 2021).

Most existing studies do not analyse individual-level migration effects, focusing instead on geographical trends, the scale of migration outflows, and general migration drivers. Furthermore, research on internal migration often relies on macro-level data, whereas our study emphasises individual-level observations. Data collected at the individual level, rather than in aggregate form, allows researchers to assess in greater detail both the factors influencing migration decisions and migration outcomes.

By doing so, this study aims to fill a gap in the literature by estimating wage gains from migration for recent graduates. The article contributes by highlighting the value of wage differences between migrants and non-migrants, which can inform policy decisions and regional development strategies.

Data & methodology

Data

The empirical part of the research is based on Monitoring of Graduates' Employment (MGE) provided by the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection and the Federal Service for Labour and Employment of the Russian Federation. It represents various datasets that combine nationwide administrative data about recent graduates. Educational data transmission is compulsorily implemented by almost all state and non-state educational organisations across the country (excluding security force organisations). It is merged with a dataset containing individual information about employment characteristics, and then supplemented with data on gender, age and the presence of various social transfers. The main advantage of MGE, in comparison with previous existing data, is the availability to analyse and evaluate the individual career and educational trajectories of graduates at the country-wide level.

Sample

In this paper, we focus exclusively on individuals who graduated in 2021 and emphasize the labour migration of university graduates. We use total monthly wages at the individual level for the period from July 2021 to July 2022. The initial sample, after removing duplicates, comprises approximately 669.000 graduates.

First, we restrict the sample to full-time bachelor's and specialist degree graduates. The resulting sample includes about 250.000 bachelors and 75.000 specialists¹. Second, additional datasets on continuing education, employment and its characteristics, as well as average admission scores to universities (i.e., average Unified State Exam grades), are merged with the educational database. Accounting for technical issues during the initial data collection, the overall sample ultimately consists of 235.400 bachelors and 70.600 specialists.

Finally, data on school education are incorporated, which are directly used in the probit regression model. Matching school-level data to the overall sample posed certain challenges; consequently, the regression sample consists of 183.266 bachelors and 26.890 specialists. To address the reduction in observations, we tested the final dataset for sample bias and confirmed its absence.

¹ A specialty is an alternative educational qualification in Russia, implying the educational program development for 5-6 years. Specialty programs are usually extended among students of technical and medical fields.

Since the MGE dataset provides only individual-level data, regional characteristics were added through the employment region variable, for which we calculated aggregate indicators. A more detailed description of all selected variables is provided in Table A1 in Appendix 1.

Method

To identify the most significant determinants of migration and to estimate the returns from migration as one of the main outcomes, we employ two distinct models. First, we implement a probit model with Heckman correction, controlling for graduates' specializations. In the context of labour migration, non-random selection may arise in the probability of employment due to unobserved values of the dependent variable. Consequently, all estimates based solely on the employed subgroup may be subject to sample selection bias. The concept of sample selection correction was introduced by J. Heckman and later extended to the evaluation of probit models using the Heckman correction (Heckman 1976; Van de Ven and Van Praag 1981).

Explanatory variables for the main equation are described in Table A1 (Appendix 1). The selection equation for employment probability includes the presence of a disability and participation in targeted training. Targeted training programs provide financial support to students during their education and require them to enter a contractual agreement with an employer, sometimes even in the early stages of their studies. Additionally, we include another variable in the selection equation, which is discussed in the Limitations section.

Second, we estimate a modified Mincer equation with Heckman correction. Given differences in both migration decisions and wages across specializations, we estimate multiple wage models. Considering disparities in labour demand, the effect of migration may vary by specialization. Accordingly, we focus on STEM fields, medical, agricultural, social sciences, humanities, and education.

The dependent variable for the probit model is a migration dummy, while for the Mincer equation we use the natural logarithm of average monthly wages.

The general equation for both models is as follows:

$$y_i^* = x_i'\beta + \varepsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

where y_i^* is the latent variable in the probit model and the main equation for the Mincer model, x_i' is the vector of explanatory variables, β is the vector of coefficients, and ε_i represents the random error term.

For the probit model, the observed migration dummy is defined as:

$$y_i^{probit} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } y_i^* > 0 \end{cases}. \quad (2)$$

Selection equation for both models:

$$z_i^* = w_i'\gamma + u_i, \quad (3)$$

where z_i^* is the latent variable in the selection equation, w_i' is the vector of explanatory variables, γ is the vector of coefficients and u_i represents the random error term.

Then the binary variable representing employment status, taking the value 1 if the individual is employed and 0 otherwise, is defined as:

$$z_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z_i^* \geq 0, \text{ i.e. } u_i \geq -w_i'\gamma, \\ 0, & \text{if } z_i^* < 0, \text{ i.e. } u_i < -w_i'\gamma. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Result for the probit model:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} y_i^{probit}, & \text{if } z_i = 1 \\ unobserved, & \text{if } z_i = 0 \end{cases} \quad i = (1, \dots, n), \tag{5}$$

where y_i represents the probability of migration, adjusted for the probability of employment, as estimated by the probit model with Heckman correction.

Result for the Mincer equation:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} y_i^{Mincer}, & \text{if } z_i = 1 \\ unobserved, & \text{if } z_i = 0 \end{cases} \quad i = (1, \dots, n), \tag{6}$$

where y_i denotes the natural logarithm of the average monthly wage, adjusted for the probability of employment, as estimated in the Mincer model with Heckman correction.

The error random terms are defined as:

$$(\varepsilon_i, u_i) \sim \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma^2 & \rho\sigma \\ \rho\sigma & 1 \end{bmatrix} \right).$$

Limitations

Although the MGE database is comprehensive, it has several limitations. First, the sample includes only officially employed graduates. If a graduate has not secured official employment after graduation, no information is available regarding their subsequent labour market outcomes. Second, the MGE contains limited information on individual characteristics and abilities and lacks data on socio-economic factors entirely. Yet, individual and family characteristics can explain a substantial portion of migration decisions as well as the returns from migration.

To address this, we use proxies for abilities, including the attainment of an honours degree and high university admission scores. We hypothesize that more capable graduates are less likely to engage in labour migration, either because they have already relocated to regions with higher-quality universities during educational migration or because they possess a competitive advantage in the local labour market. Additionally, we consider selection prior to university, reflected in the possession of a school certificate with honours.

First, school achievements serve as early indicators of ability, while a university diploma with honours reflects post-graduation competence. Second, we hypothesize that graduates with honours certificates who did not migrate during educational migration are less likely to migrate during the labour market stage. A school certificate with honours thus acts as a proxy for abilities in the transition from secondary to higher education. High-performing individuals are more likely to obtain quality higher education and acquire specific skills demanded in the labour market. Such graduates enjoy competitive advantages locally and, *ceteris paribus*, are less likely to relocate, particularly if they already have employment and established social networks. Consequently, this variable is included in the selection equation of the probit model as an instrumental variable to correct for selection bias before the school-to-work transition. So, in the selection equation of the Heckman probit model, we include three variables: disability, participation in targeted training, and school performance.

It is also important to note that we do not focus on the duration of an individual's stay in the destination region; therefore, migration is not classified as short- or long-term. Additionally, this paper places less emphasis on the effects of regional characteristics.

Findings

Descriptive statistics

The main factors significantly influencing migration decisions in our study are related to educational and job characteristics (Table 1). First, we hypothesize that graduates enrolled in paid-basis programs are more likely to migrate, as they may seek to recoup their educational investments in more economically developed regions. Second, we expect that holding a diploma with honours and participation in continuing education will reduce the probability of labour migration. Third, working while studying may slow migration and bind graduates to their region of study due to established labour market networks.

Fourth, higher university admission scores are likely associated with a lower probability of migration. A higher score indicates better quality education and a more economically developed region. In such regions, high labour demand can compress wages from below. For graduates with lower abilities, this may translate into higher potential returns from migration, thereby encouraging relocation. Finally, we anticipate that gender will have either a weak or negligible effect on migration probability since both female and male graduates are in the early stages of their careers.

Table 1. The proportion of migrated graduates by educational and job characteristics

Factors	Leaving by, %
<i>Source of educational funding</i>	
Budgetary	30.6
Private	34.2
<i>Diploma with honours</i>	
Yes	29.0
No	32.7
<i>Further education</i>	
Yes	26.4
No	34.6
<i>Average score of university admission</i>	
64.0 and less	34.0
64.1–74.0	33.9
74.1–85.0	25.1
More than 85.0	17.5
<i>Gender</i>	
Male	33.1
Female	31.1
<i>Work while education</i>	
Yes	33.1
No	31.2

Source: authors' calculations, MGE

According to the MGE data, the total share of employed graduates in 2021 who migrated to work in another region amounted to 31.8%. Graduates relocate both to economically developed regions near their place of education and to major urban agglomerations, with Moscow emerging as the primary destination. The by-region matrix (Table A2, Appendix 1) shows that, on average, almost 13% of graduates from all federal districts leave their educational regions for Moscow, with the largest number relocating from nearby areas, including the Moscow Oblast. Beyond the central part of Russia, graduates also tend to migrate to regions close to their region of study.

High salaries in the Far Eastern and Ural regions are associated with a lower rate of graduate labour migration. Economic activity in these regions is largely based on natural resource extraction, providing employees with a competitive wage advantage. In contrast, economic specialization in the Caucasian and Southern regions, primarily in agriculture, encourages graduates to migrate to more technically developed regions. Consequently, wages in “outsider” regions are almost six times lower than in leading regions: North Ossetia – 23.100 rubles; the average across all regions – 50.200 rubles (Table A1, Appendix 1); Chukotka – 126.500 rubles).

Wages, along with certain educational and labour characteristics, are correlated with the probability of migration, particularly when considering educational specializations (Table 2). The largest share of migrants is observed among graduates in agricultural fields, who also earn the lowest wages. At the same time, they are the least likely to enrol in paid-basis programs, have the lowest average admission exam scores and perform near the average on other indicators.

Table 2. Statistics on the main educational and employment variables by each specialization

Specialization	Migration, %	Diploma with honours, %	Private funding, %	Average exam score	Employment, %	Work while education, %	Average wage, thousand rubles		
							Stay	Leave	Wage gap, %
STEM	31.9	18.2	10.9	68.7	77.2	49.9	57.8	61.5	6.0
Medicine	31.1	12.8	38.8	70.3	78.8	57.6	53.1	57.0	6.8
Agriculture	36.2	18.3	0.05	59.2	71.3	46.0	37.5	41.0	8.5
Social	34.2	22.0	73.4	69.1	70.9	42.6	45.2	44.4	-1.8
Education	24.4	26.8	18.3	67.2	78.7	52.6	43.0	46.2	6.9
Humanities	30.7	29.7	48.6	71.4	64.3	33.8	40.8	42.6	4.2
Mean	31.8	20.4	37.5	68.7	74.4	47.5	46.2	48.8	-

Source: authors’ calculations, MGE

Graduates in social sciences, by contrast, are the most likely to pursue education on a paid basis but also receive below-average wages. Notably, they are the only group that experiences a wage loss upon migration (-1.8%).

Migration patterns among STEM, medical, and humanities graduates are generally comparable to the average for all specializations. Engineers, mathematicians, and specialists in natural sciences tend to earn relatively high salaries and often relocate to regions with technological hubs that provide specialized educational and employment infrastructure (Emelina et al. 2022). Medical graduates are less likely to obtain honours degrees and,

in nearly 40% of cases, pay for their education. They benefit from both relatively high salaries and some of the largest gains from migration.

Humanities graduates lead in many educational indicators but perform poorly in most employment-related measures. Nearly 30% hold diplomas with honours, and they have the highest university admission scores. Nevertheless, they are employed less frequently than graduates in other fields, and their average wages reach only 81% of the overall average for all other specializations, both in their region of study and after relocation.

Graduates in education represent a distinct group of specialists, characterized by a consistently high employment rate (78.7%) but relatively low wages. This “stability” is largely associated with the historically low funding for the education sector in Russia (Emelina et al. 2022). Education graduates also include a high proportion of top-performing individuals, as well as graduates who were employed during their studies. Many of them pursue continuing education (34%), which further contributes to a lower likelihood of migration.

Thus, we observe potential differences both in migration decisions and, in particular, in the outcomes of migration among graduates of different specializations. Consequently, we anticipate disparities in both the probability of migration and the returns from migration across the six groups of specializations. Specialization is included in the Heckman-corrected probit model as a categorical variable, while Mincer equations are estimated for each specialty separately.

Regression results

Probit-model

Labour market and migration outcomes, presented in Tables A3 and A4 (Appendix 2), refer to the first year after graduation, corresponding to the early stages of graduates’ careers.

First, according to Table A3, regional factors have a relatively weak effect on migration decisions compared with other characteristics. The largest contributions come from the average regional wage and the subsistence minimum. An increase in the average wage in the region of employment is associated with a 1.3% higher probability of migration, whereas a rise in the subsistence minimum is associated with a nearly 3% decrease in migration probability. The latter finding is not trivial; we hypothesize that the negative relationship between the subsistence minimum and internal migration reflects regional labour market specifics. The highest subsistence minimum values are observed in the Far Eastern, Ural, and Siberian regions, which are characterized by high wages and harsh living and working conditions. In these cases, migration returns may function as a form of monetary compensation.

Second, educational characteristics make the most significant contribution to migration decisions. Compared with social sciences graduates, the probability of migration decreases for all other specializations except medical sciences. Education graduates are 6.4% less likely to migrate, whereas medical graduates relocate to another region 1.5% more often. This pattern may be driven by shortages of qualified medical personnel in many northern and eastern regions of Russia, where relocation is likely accompanied by substantial wage increases. Interestingly, enrolment in paid-basis programs has a small but unexpectedly negative impact on the likelihood of migration. This may indicate that such graduates either remain in their region of study to recoup educational costs or delay relocation for other reasons.

Continuing education and holding a diploma with honours predictably reduce the probability of labour migration by 6.0% and 1.9%, respectively. Our hypothesis regarding the

negative impact of university admission scores on migration probability is also confirmed. The lower migration propensity among more capable graduates may additionally be explained by their higher likelihood of working while studying (21% vs. 19% among graduates with regular diplomas). For these graduates, the transition from study to work is relatively smooth, but the costs associated with relocation are significantly higher.

Furthermore, the probability of migration decreases by 0.85% for graduates who worked while studying. Combining education with employment is particularly important in the early stages of a career, providing a comparative advantage in the labour market. Such experience also affords valuable job networks and communication skills. However, relocation may act as a deterrent due to the loss of familiar working conditions and established networks, which can be considered a cost of migration.

Gender differences in migration probability among recent graduates are small, with men being 1.1% more likely than women to relocate. Age profiles indicate that migration decisions for both genders coincide at an early age, after which men tend to migrate slightly more frequently (Mkrtchyan et al. 2020).

Mincer equation

The primary and most significant finding from the Mincer equation is the contribution of migration to wages (Table A4 of Appendix 2). Overall, migration increases wages by 10.7%. Controlling for regions with the highest average wages, the salary gains from relocation are even more pronounced. Graduates can therefore expect returns from migration of up to 17% when controlling Moscow, Saint Petersburg, or the main mining regions of the Urals, Far East, and Northwest.

At the same time, migration returns vary by specialty. For instance, graduates in social sciences and education experience relatively modest returns from migration, at 4.0% and 5.8%, respectively. Social sciences graduates often face job mismatches, as many hold degrees in fields that primarily develop general human capital, leading to employment in low-paid positions. Education graduates traditionally earn low wages due to chronic underfunding in the sector, which negatively affects their returns from migration.

The highest returns from migration are observed among medical graduates, at 15.8%. Medical graduates also exhibit the highest employment rates and are more likely to have worked during their studies, which contributes positively to wages through the accumulation of practical skills. The high salaries observed in 2021 may additionally reflect COVID-19-related compensation. STEM and agricultural graduates also benefit substantially from migration, with returns of 13.5% and 15.3%, respectively. STEM graduates are more likely to secure comparable or higher-paying positions, reflecting the strong demand for digital and technical competencies in the Russian labour market, which are critical for implementing innovative economic development. For agricultural graduates, the observed wage increases post-migration can be partly explained by the low-base effect due to existing discrepancies between labour supply and demand in the agricultural sector.

Educational characteristics further exert a significant impact on wages. University admission scores play a particularly important role: graduates from universities with entrance scores of above 64 points tend to enjoy greater returns from migration. The effect is especially pronounced for selective universities, where average scores are 85 or above. STEM graduates, in particular, experience substantial wage gains, consistent with the high demand for such specialists in the Russian labour market. Many of these graduates also aim to enter universities with high-quality programs, providing them with the conditions necessary for wage growth.

Discussion

This article focuses on the analysis of migration decisions and the returns to internal migration among qualified Russian graduates. As previously noted, the Russian economy exhibits specific institutional characteristics across both regional economies and educational institutions (Oshchepkov and Kapelyushnikov 2015). Our study contributes to the understanding of graduates' migration decisions by simultaneously considering educational and labour market characteristics. Unlike prior studies, we employ individual-level data, which allows for a direct linkage between education and labour market outcomes. Taking into account regional differences in education, the article examines both the factors affecting the probability of internal migration and the potential gains or losses from relocation across various groups of specializations.

The results regarding migration incentives align with findings from both Russian and international studies (Di Cintio and Grassi 2011; Liu and Shen 2014; Mkrtchyan and Florinskaya 2018a, 2018b; Vakulenko 2019; Borzykh 2022). The paper also highlights important findings related to migration-related wage gains. We observe substantial wage differentiation among Russian regions across all analyses, including sub-sample estimations. Many of these differences are explained by educational characteristics. Whereas previous Russian studies predominantly focused on regional, socio-economic, and macroeconomic determinants of migration (Vakulenko et al. 2011; Mkrtchyan and Vakulenko 2019; Vakulenko 2019; Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2021), some research emphasizes the crucial role of the education system in the effective functioning of the labour market (Borzykh 2022).

Many of our results are consistent with previous studies, particularly regarding the migration structure (Mkrtchyan et al. 2020) and the impact of educational and employment characteristics on wages (Rudakov et al. 2019; Rozhkova et al. 2021; Borzykh 2022; Emelina et al. 2022). Furthermore, our findings demonstrate robustness. A comparison of the graduates' migration matrix by federal districts (Table A2, Appendix 1) with the corresponding matrix for 2018 graduates (Emelina et al. 2022) shows similar migration flows, primarily directed toward major economic centres, especially Moscow and St. Petersburg. Our research reinforces the necessity for closer alignment between the education system and the labour market to improve graduate outcomes at the start of their careers.

In addition to the technical limitations described in the Data & Methodology section, there are several practical restrictions. First, we do not differentiate between graduates who continue their education after obtaining a bachelor's or specialist degree and those who have completed their studies. As the true motives for relocation are not observable, graduates who continue their studies are included in the sample as part of the labour force. However, comparisons between these two groups may yield somewhat different results. Second, we do not isolate the temporary effects of migration. We assume that labour market outcomes change over time following relocation, which could be explored in future research.

Conclusion

Internal migration of graduates, as an important component of the Russian economy, leaves a significant imprint on the development of individual regions. While numerous factors influence the probability of migration among Russian graduates, educational and employ-

ment characteristics play a particularly important role in shaping both migration decisions and outcomes. The results obtained are consistent with previous studies and underscore that internal migration is often the only way for graduates to enhance career opportunities and increase wages. Graduates in medicine and agriculture gain the greatest benefits from migration, whereas STEM graduates occupy the most advantageous positions across nearly all indicators.

Despite the high quality of life in many Russian regions and growing access to higher education, substantial migration flows of young people leaving their native regions to improve their financial status are still observed. Accordingly, wage increases appear to be one of the primary motives for relocation. This suggests that improvements in regional living conditions (e.g., infrastructure, quality of social services, climate) may sometimes be secondary when individuals make migration decisions. Moreover, under conditions of pronounced regional and sectoral differentiation in labour markets, youth migration is likely to persist. In light of this, it is necessary to strengthen policies aimed at better aligning educational institutions with labour market demands. Such measures would improve the migration outcomes of graduates, enhancing their efficiency in both monetary and non-monetary terms.

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Appendix 1

Table A1. Descriptive statistics for the selected variables

Groups of variables	Mean	Sample share, %	N	Data source
Probability of migration (1 – migrated)	0.35	-	228022	MGE
<i>Educational</i>				
Specialization	-	100.0	306417	
1. STEM (Mathematics, Natural sciences, Engineering)	-	36.5	111682	
2. Healthcare and Medical sciences	-	11.1	33859	
3. Agricultural science	-	3.8	11767	
4. Social sciences (Economics, Law, Sociology, Psychology)	-	33.1	101647	
5. Education	-	9.4	28718	MGE
6. Humanities (Philology, Linguistics, Cultural studies, Arts)	-	6.1	18717	
Source of educational funding (1 – private)	0.38	-	306354	
Diploma with honours (1 – yes)	0.20	-	305972	
Further education (1 – yes)	0.32	-	306417	
Average university admission score (points)	68.7	-	300693	
<i>Employment</i>				
Average monthly wage per region (thousands of rubles)	50.2	-	228022	
Average monthly wage per region in case of migration (thousands of rubles)	52.3	-	228022	MGE
Work experience (years)	1.9	-	306417	
Work while education (1 – yes)	0.47	-	306417	
<i>Personal</i>				
Age (years)	22.7	-	306417	
Gender (1 – male)	0.42	-	306417	MGE
<i>Regional</i>				
Life expectancy at birth (years)	70.8	-	306417	
Subsistence minimum (thousands of rubles)	12.8	-	306417	
Prices for secondary housing (thousands of rubles per sq. metre)	105.5	-	306417	Federal State Statistics Service
Population density (person per sq. kilometre)	1374.3	-	306417	

Groups of variables	Mean	Sample share, %	N	Data source
Unemployment rate (%)	4.4	-	306417	Federal State Statistics Service Ministry of Culture of the Russian Federation
Emissions of air pollutants waste from stationary and mobile sources (thousands of tons)	390.9	-	306417	
Number of museums and theaters (units)	90.1	-	306417	

Source: authors' calculations

Table A2. By-region migration matrix, % of employed graduates

Educational regions and federal districts	Regions and federal districts of work									
	Central	Northwestern	Southern	North Caucasian	Volga	Ural	Siberian	Far Eastern	Moscow	Saint-Petersburg
Central	68.7	1.3	1.7	0.2	2.8	0.6	0.5	0.5	20.6	3.1
Northwestern	3.2	73.4	1.2	0.1	1.9	0.8	0.6	0.5	8.8	9.4
Southern	3.3	0.8	71.3	1.7	2.2	1.3	0.6	0.6	14.9	3.2
North Caucasian	2.9	0.6	5.4	68.6	2.6	1.3	0.6	0.5	14.5	3
Volga	3.7	0.7	1.5	0.4	71.8	2.7	0.7	0.4	14.8	3.3
Ural	1.6	0.5	1	0.1	3.2	78.6	1.9	0.7	9.8	2.5
Siberian	2.4	0.7	1	0.1	1.1	2.4	76.6	2.2	10	3.5
Far Eastern	2.1	0.6	0.7	0.1	0.8	0.7	3.7	80.1	7.9	3.2
Moscow	12.6	0.6	0.9	0.4	1.7	1.1	0.7	0.5	79.3	2.3
Saint-Petersburg	2.8	7.4	1.3	0.3	2.2	1.5	1.1	1	14.5	67.9

Source: authors' calculations, MGE

Appendix 2

Table A3. Marginal Effects from the Heckman Probit Model. Dependent variable in the full model: probability of migration

Variables	Without a correction for school diploma with honours	With a correction for school diploma with honours
<i>Regional factors</i>		
Life expectancy at birth	0.0288*** (0.000719)	0.00435*** (0.000908)
Unemployment rate	-0.00377*** (0.000471)	0.00383*** (0.000514)
Average regional wage	0.0154*** (0.000224)	0.0133*** (9.09e-05)
Subsistence minimum	-0.0227*** (0.000736)	-0.0302*** (0.000567)
Prices for secondary housing	-0.00107*** (7.40e-05)	-0.000827*** (8.18e-05)
Emissions of air pollutants waste	-9.13e-05*** (2.05e-06)	-4.64e-05*** (2.20e-06)
Population density	-4.26e-05*** (1.75e-06)	1.30e-06 (1.98e-06)
Number of museums and theatres	0.000866*** (3.31e-05)	-0.000146*** (4.23e-05)
<i>Educational factors</i>		
Average university admission score	-0.00854*** (0.000114)	-0.00207*** (0.000158)
Source of educational funding (1 = private)	-0.00419** (0.00195)	-0.00207 (0.00246)
Further education (1 = yes)	-0.0515*** (0.00166)	-0.0602*** (0.00197)
Diploma with honors (1 = yes)	-0.0166*** (0.00187)	-0.0187*** (0.00224)
<i>Specialization (base – social science)</i>		
STEM	-0.0119*** (0.00227)	-0.0168*** (0.00272)
Medicine	0.0287*** (0.00317)	0.0146** (0.00618)

Variables	Without a correction for school diploma with honours	With a correction for school diploma with honours
Agriculture	-0.0352*** (0.00409)	-0.00123 (0.00571)
Education	-0.0521*** (0.00284)	-0.0644*** (0.00332)
Humanities	-0.00646* (0.00356)	-0.0155*** (0.00406)
<i>Employment factors</i>		
Work while education (1 = yes)	-0.0231*** (0.00158)	-0.00857*** (0.00189)
<i>Personal factors</i>		
Gender (1 = male)	0.00582*** (0.00166)	0.0114*** (0.00204)
Age	-0.0274*** (0.00272)	-0.0379 (0.0306)
Age ²	0.000442*** (4.69e-05)	0.000712 (0.000683)
N	223 434	154 543

Source: authors' calculations, MGE. Notes: Standard errors in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Table A4. Results from the Mincer Equation. Marginal effects; dependent variable: natural logarithm of total monthly wage

Variables	Specializations						
	Total + Regions	1	2	3	4	5	6
	Total	STEM	Medicine	Agriculture	Social	Education	Humanities
Migration	0.107*** (0.00311)	0.135*** (0.00522)	0.158*** (0.0104)	0.153*** (0.0141)	0.0402*** (0.00559)	0.0579*** (0.00985)	0.0907*** (0.0139)
Work experience	0.130*** (0.00143)	0.157*** (0.00258)	0.101*** (0.00382)	0.109*** (0.00569)	0.152*** (0.00301)	0.104*** (0.00380)	0.154*** (0.00673)
Work experience ²	-0.00450*** (7.40e-05)	-0.00625*** (0.000149)	-0.00330*** (0.000189)	-0.00344*** (0.000250)	-0.00589*** (0.000228)	-0.00375*** (0.000216)	-0.00543*** (0.000364)
Work while education (1 = yes)	0.0773*** (0.00353)	0.129*** (0.00603)	0.0333*** (0.0126)	0.0420*** (0.0161)	0.0120* (0.00646)	-0.00821 (0.0101)	0.00639 (0.0149)
Gender (1 = male)	0.122*** (0.00324)	0.223*** (0.00506)	-0.00726 (0.0107)	0.180*** (0.0143)	-0.00189 (0.00589)	0.0146 (0.0120)	0.0647*** (0.0171)
Source of education (1 = private)	-0.0240*** (0.00375)	-0.0152* (0.00809)	-0.147*** (0.0106)	0.0515 (0.0351)	-0.0163*** (0.00626)	0.0298*** (0.0113)	0.0183 (0.0133)
Further education (1 = yes)	-0.0695*** (0.00322)	-0.137*** (0.00494)	0.0532 (0.0512)	-0.00364 (0.0147)	-0.0223*** (0.00582)	0.0547*** (0.00904)	-0.0878*** (0.0141)
Diploma with honours (1 = yes)	0.0799*** (0.00363)	0.122*** (0.00622)	-0.103*** (0.0144)	0.0910*** (0.0176)	0.107*** (0.00658)	-0.00292 (0.00976)	0.0442*** (0.0143)
		<i>Average university admission score (base = 64.0 and less)</i>					
64.1-74.0	0.0635*** (0.00361)	0.106*** (0.00586)	-0.00982 (0.0157)	0.177*** (0.0160)	0.00812 (0.00651)	0.0680*** (0.0104)	0.0789*** (0.0187)

Variables	Total	Total + Regions	Specializations					
			1	2	3	4	5	6
			STEM	Medicine	Agriculture	Social	Education	Humanities
74.1-85.0	0.381*** (0.00469)	0.157*** (0.00524)	0.391*** (0.00772)	0.200*** (0.0178)		0.400*** (0.00827)	0.266*** (0.0167)	0.359*** (0.0212)
More than 85.0	0.689*** (0.00751)	0.402*** (0.00797)	0.734*** (0.0118)	0.265*** (0.101)		0.602*** (0.0117)	0.297** (0.133)	0.571*** (0.0279)
			<i>Specialization (base - social science)</i>					
STEM	0.180*** (0.00435)	0.191*** (0.00422)						
Medicine	0.0798*** (0.00529)	0.152*** (0.00515)						
Agriculture	-0.107*** (0.00842)	-0.0890*** (0.00817)						
Education	-0.00646 (0.00565)	0.0331*** (0.00546)						
Humanities	-0.112*** (0.00675)	-0.0918*** (0.00652)						
			<i>Top-wage regions of work</i>					
Moscow		0.441*** (0.00431)						
Saint-Petersburg		0.191*** (0.00545)						
Chukotka		0.374** (0.174)						

Variables	Total	Specializations						
		Total + Regions	1	2	3	4	5	6
			STEM	Medicine	Agriculture	Social	Education	Humanities
Kamchatka		0.505*** (0.0476)						
Sakhalin		0.628*** (0.0467)						
Magadan		0.743*** (0.0578)						
Tumen (with Yamal and Khanty-Mansi)		0.320*** (0.0107)						
Murmansk		0.381*** (0.0308)						
Sakha (Yakutia)		0.416*** (0.0186)						
N	223 427	223 427	83 716	26 679	8 364	70 529	22 347	11 792

Source: authors' calculations, MGE. Notes: Standard errors in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1. The wage premium in all Mincer equations is calculated using the following formula: $\frac{w-w_0}{w_0} = e^{\beta} - 1$.